

Results and Discussion

The complexes sl. nos. 1–7 (Table 1) have 1 : 2 (metal–ligand) stoichiometry. The base seems to facilitate deprotonation of the phenolic group and consequent formation of Zn–O bond. Extremely low values of molar conductances Λ_M indicate non-ionic nature. The broad ir band at 3 100–2 700 cm^{-1} (OH phenolic) for the free ligands, are absent in the spectra of the complexes sl. nos. 1–7 suggesting coordination of phenolic oxygen to Zn^{II} with loss of the phenolic proton. A marginal (10 cm^{-1}) downward displacement of the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the ligands (1 630–1 610 cm^{-1}) in the complexes indicated $\text{C}=\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Zn}$ bond formation³. The 500–490 and 425–380 cm^{-1} bands were assigned to Z–O and Z–N modes, respectively^{3,4}.

The broad pmr signal of the free ligands at δ 12.7–14 (intramolecularly H-bonded phenolic groups) was absent in the spectra of the complexes sl. nos. 1 and 2, thus confirming the deprotonation of the phenolic groups on complex formation. Other signals observed were as expected. However, the signal for the proton attached to the aldehydic carbon displayed a marginal up-field shift, contrary to the expectation. The magnitude of this displacement was found to be δ 0.28 and 0.12 in case of bis(*N*-benzylsalicylaldimine) zinc(II) and its *N*-phenylethyl counterpart, respectively. Theoretically a down-field shift is more likely due to deshielding that occurs in consequence of drainage of electrons from azomethine nitrogen atom while bonding ($\text{C}=\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Zn}$) to the central metal atom. However, the observed behaviour remains unexplained at present.

The complexes sl. nos. 8–10 in absence of a base were well-defined compounds (Table 1). Analytical data of the complexes are consistent with the composition $\text{ZnCl}_2 : (\text{LH})_2$, where LH = Schiff base ligand molecule. A fourth complex was obtained from the sticky mass and could not be properly investigated. Two possible structures can be envisaged for these compounds. Extremely low values of molar conductances in nitrobenzene apparently suggests the formation of $[(\text{LH})_2\text{ZnCl}_2]$ and rules out the possibility of $[(\text{LH})_2\text{Zn}]^{2+}\text{Cl}_2^-$. In methanol solution, conductance value increased with time and reached a limiting value within 24 h at room temperature. This can satisfactorily be explained presuming the release of chloride ions,

Attempts to prepare $\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ complexes with Schiff bases derived from 3- NO_2 - and 5- NO_2 -salicylaldehydes did not succeed presumably due to the presence of strong electron-withdrawing nitro group rendering the phenolic group acidic to the extent that they ionise completely even in absence of a base.

The ir spectra of complexes sl. nos. 8–10 show the presence of a broad ν_{OH} band extending over the region 3 250–2 500 cm^{-1} indicating thereby the presence of phenolic-OH group in these complexes. The up-field shift of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ by about 10 cm^{-1} with complexes sl. nos. 8–10 were attributed to the breakdown of H-bonded ($\text{C}=\text{N} \cdot \text{H}-\text{O}$) structure in the ligand on complex formation. The bands around 470 and 450–415 cm^{-1} were tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{N}}$ modes. The $\nu_{\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}}$ bands expected below 300 cm^{-1} could not be recorded due to limitations of the instrument.

In the pmr spectra slight down-field shift of the signal for the proton attached to the aldehydic carbon atom further supported the coordination of the azomethine group to Zn^{II} . Signals corresponding to the phenolic protons were considerably displaced ($\delta > 1$) down-field in δ 11.6–12.6 region, supporting the conjecture that the phenolic group is only weakly coordinated in these compounds.

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Synthetic and Biocidal Studies of some Bivalent Metal Complexes of Benzaldehyde-salicyloylhydrazones

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WE describe here the complexes of bivalent Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with benzaldehyde-salicyloylhydrazone (BSH or HL). The complexes were characterised by elemental, magnetic, conductance and ir and electron spectral data. Biocidal activity of the metal chelates on fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *A. nidulans* at 37° in agar agar culture media was found to be several folds higher than that of BSH.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand (BSH) was synthesised¹ by condensing salicylhydrazide with benzaldehyde in equimolar amounts, and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (70%). The metal complexes were synthesised by reported procedure². The purity of the compounds was tested by tlc. Elemental analysis

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was done at D.R.D.E., Gwalior, molecular weights were determined cryscopically in DMSO. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} , and electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Unicem SP-500 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature using Gouy balance. Molar conductance were measured in DMSO using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the metal complexes (Table 1) indicate 1:2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. Low molar conductance values (5–11 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in DMSO (0.001 M) indicate their non-ionic nature⁵.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF BENZALDEHYDE-SALICYLOYLHYDRAZONE AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Mol. wt. Found/Calcd.	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.	
				N	Metal
BSH(HL)	209	238.47 (240.10)	—	11.42 (11.71)	—
Co(L) ₂	290	532.42 (536.98)	4.95	10.41 (10.42)	11.03 (10.97)
Ni(L) ₂	240	531.73 (536.69)	3.10	10.50 (10.43)	11.03 (10.93)
Cu(L) ₂	235	537.26 (541.54)	1.83	10.01 (9.97)	12.02 (11.73)
Zn(L) ₂	280	539.45 (543.38)	Dimag.	10.53 (10.30)	12.17 (12.03)

In the ir spectra of the metal complexes, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the ligand at 1 630 cm^{-1} is lowered by 40–70 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ at 1 560 cm^{-1} lowered⁴ by 30–50 cm^{-1} . Positions of the other bands remain almost unaltered. This fact indicates the coordination of BSH to the metal ion, both through azomethine nitrogen as well as amide oxygen. Further, the disappearance of the ν_{OH} (3 260 cm^{-1}) and shifting of the phenolic $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (1 210 cm^{-1}) towards higher region by 25–40 cm^{-1} indicate the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through phenolic oxygen⁵ as well. Thus the ligand provides monoanionic ONO tridentate chelation. Some new bands found in the far-ir spectra of the chelates around 530–540, 440–445 and 350–380 cm^{-1} also supports the formation of M–O, M–N and M–O–C bonds, respectively, in the metal complexes^{6–8}.

μ_{eff} value of the Cu^{II} complex was 1.83 B.M. A broad band at 14 850 cm^{-1} in the absorption spectra and two sholder peaks at 12 930 and 22 325 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions suggest its distorted octahedral geometry⁷. The position of the bands around 9 899, 16 573 and 24 969 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} chelate can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, and the

μ_{eff} value of 3.1 B.M. suggest an octahedral geometry around the metal ion¹⁰. Similarly, the bands around 7 624, 16 366 and 19 950 cm^{-1} in the Co^{II} complex due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions and the μ_{eff} value of 4.95 B.M. are in conformity with a distorted octahedral geometry^{11–13}. The ligand field parameters such as 10Dq, B, β and LFSE calculated for the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes corroborate it. The Zn^{II} complex was diamagnetic as expected.

Biocidal activity: The ligand (BSH) and its metal complexes (Table 1) were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *A. nidulence* in agar agar culture media at 37°. The results showed that the metal chelates were more fungitoxic compared to the ligand. This increase in fungitoxicity is probably either due to the faster diffusion of metal chelates as a whole through the cell membrane or due to the combined activity effect of the metal and ligand¹⁴.

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